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IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE FIELD OF PREVENTION AND LIMITATION OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Annotation. This article discusses the main directions for improving the State System for Prevention and Response to Emergency Situations (SSES). Some methodological and theoretical aspects of the development of an emergency management system are described. The current plans and prospects of the State Emergency Service are also considered.

Key words: State Emergency Service, emergency situations, Ministry of Emergency Situations, safety, fires, accident, catastrophe, man-made, environmental, natural disasters.

For any person, security is the most important value, and the presence of that security gives a citizen the opportunity to calmly build his life and conduct various types of activities. The State System for the Prevention and Elimination of Emergency Situations (SSES) is responsible for ensuring the safety of the population from emergency situations and their consequences in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the definition given in the Regulations on the State

Emergency Service [1], this is “a system of executive authorities of the Republic and local governments, government agencies and various public associations, as well as specially authorized structures with the forces and means available to them designed to prevent emergency situations, and in case of their occurrence - to eliminate them, ensure the safety of the population, protect the environment and reduce losses and material damage.

The main purpose of creating the State Emergency Service was to unite the efforts of state authorities and local governments and organizations, their forces and means in the field of emergency prevention and response.

The goal of the State Emergency Service is a timely, effective response with society’s resources to emergency threats and their manifestations, and further decomposition of this goal.

Social significance and the emergence of more and more new dangers for the well-being of the population of the Republic provide grounds for constant improving this system in order to be able to prevent and eliminate an emergency situation as efficiently and timely as possible in all parts of the Republic and for any period of time.

According to the development plan of the State Emergency Service, developed by the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to improve activities in the field of prevention and response to emergency situations, it is necessary to solve the following problems in the near future:

1. To finally complete the creation of a territorially distributed system for alerting the population about the occurrence of natural disasters, to create comprehensive monitoring systems for economic facilities, to significantly strengthen their instrumentation and analytical base, facilitating the formation of a full-fledged territorial forecast.

2. It is necessary to carry out microseismic zoning and earthquake-resistant

construction in hazardous areas at an accelerated pace.

3. Increase the readiness of the healthcare system and bioengineering science to combat foci of exotic infections, improve technologies for the production and testing of vaccines and antidotes.

4. In the territories it is necessary to form ecological protection zones for water sources and construct water storage tanks.

5. Continue the development of a system for training the population to act in the event of regional disasters.

According to the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic, the so-called human factor will remain the main cause of major accidents and fires. A high level of accidents will continue in a number of important sectors of the economy, such as transport, energy, housing and communal services, and some others. People's increasing dependence on technology and innovation will contribute to the possibility of cascading disasters. [3].

In this regard, in the Republic it is necessary to implement the long-overdue modernization of the personnel training system, which focuses on competence and strict implementation of technological discipline.

The resources of enterprises must be consistently concentrated on updating production. Also, the actual content of supervision over supposed sources of emergency situations should be changed in order to improve the functioning of the system. It is worth organizing monitoring of technological processes, which in its pre-emergency and emergency parts will become an integral part of monitoring emergency situations, which will require the integration of information resources of Gostekhnadzor and the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic. [4].

One of the important aspects of the development of the emergency management system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the formation of a system of interaction between the state, society and the individual in matters of protection from natural and man-made emergencies. [5].

It is necessary to develop and form a common information and management system that will ensure operational interaction and response of forces and means involved in eliminating natural emergencies, major fires, and responding to wartime threats.

The priority should be a unified technological chain for protecting the population and territories: monitoring-assessment-response-interaction - effective assistance. In constantly changing conditions, a monitoring and forecasting system and various express methods for identifying and diagnosing hazards must be developed. [6], [7].

An important factor is warning and informing the population about emergency threats. New methods of using various types of communications are being developed - social networks, the blogosphere, SMS notifications, etc. The mutual penetration of the Internet and television, the development of telecommunications and information technologies makes it possible to notify the population in the shortest possible time.

A new concept of information policy is being developed, where the range of propaganda, educational, and information forms of interaction with the population has been significantly expanded.

Supervision over the condition of the most important facilities in the energy, transport, and housing and communal services sectors will be strengthened. Ensuring the safety of people also applies to militarized mine rescue units. To create an effective emergency response system, the material and technical base of the VGSCCh (militarized mine rescue units) is being modernized.

To ensure safety at water bodies, the work of the State Inspectorate for Water Resources is being improved.

In large populated cities, emergency rescue complexes are created to ensure emergency rescue operations, conduct operational monitoring and exchange information.

The most important aspect of the further development of the State Emergency Service system is international cooperation. With international cooperation, a methodology for operational information exchange between crisis centers is being developed, thereby ensuring the construction of an effective global system of coordination and management in emergency situations.

There is still a lot to be done to improve the functioning of the State Emergency Service at different levels of management, but the most important thing is to focus on solving priority tasks using the “single team” principle, where each specialist is able to competently and skillfully solve the assigned tasks, thereby ensuring the safety of people’s health and lives.

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